
Creativity Versus Indian Education System: A Critical Study on Chetan Bhagat's Book, Five Point Someone and its Film Version.

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Abstract:

Chetan Bhagat is one of the greatest Indian authors. His work is basically based on Indian education system which lacks the proper modifications of the Indian education process. He raises the questions on non- creative process of learning education from Indian institutions. He thus,wrote five important selling novels which hold its proper destination to enlighten the thought process of Indian common people.The novels,"Five Point Someone"(2004),"One Night The Call Centre"(2005),"The Three Mistakes of My Life"(2008),"2 States"(2009),"Revolution"(2020) bear the testimony of changing the traditional approach of learning through adopting the global process of education. His debut novel "Five Point Someone" or its subtitle "What Not to Do at IIT" explores a very unique problem of Indian education system and tries to seek out an alternative method by emphasizing on modern education system of the world which is basically formed on creativity. The novel,"Five Point Someone" bears extreme ideas about the structural lack of the Indian education system. Through this novel, Bhagat shows the huge difference between Indian education system and the thought process of the learners. There is no proper scope to explore their innovative ideas of the learners as there is a specific structure to learn education. The creative learners do not find definite places to invent new things. As a result the overall development of the learners does not exist at the final stage of their lives. Chetan Bhagat through exposing this vital problems attempts to concern to the common people and also suggests to change the education system so that there would be wide place for the learners to show their versatile abilities under any institutions of India. Thus, this paper will be writing on researching the whole process of Indian education system in contrast with innovative countries of the world.

Introduction:

"High scores do not necessarily equate to effective learning and the onus of education is being defeated in the competitive mad race of marks."(Education Times by A.K. Bakshi) .The Indian education system holds pupils to an one confined place. This process makes them follow to an one destination. They did not get the proper place to show their latent talents. According to reliable study 98% of the kids at the time of

entering school think different but when they go through the education system, at the age of 25, only 2 % of the pupils think different. This happens so because our education system from childhood provides ready-made answers to the questions and hence strip the learners of their ability to think from their's own. It discourages questioning, discovery, experimentation and application in the class room and thus draws them in rote learning. This situation is further aggravated by very heavy and outdated syllabi. Exams have become just 'mugging up' and memory test. We should understand that good marks do not necessarily equate to effective learning and the onus of education is being defeated in the competitive mad race of high marks. We must come out from such burden education system where students do not able to focus on their individuals' difference. Every learners has their own different abilities to learn different things. But our education system follows a same pattern for all students. As a result we do not get expected output from them. This collective rigid method of Indian education does not able to grip the creative abilities of the learners. Thus the final achievement of our students do not reach to the all round development and hence the rank of Indian education system becomes low in comparison with other countries.

Chetan Bhagat's novel "Five Point Someone" and it's adopted film "3 Idiots" challenges the traditional approach of learning education and positivizes the modern education system of the world which is basically focused on innovative and creative thinking of the learners. Bhagat exposes the narrow-mindedness of the teachers and the parents through this novel. There are various problems in the society which creates such atmosphere of narrow thinking about education. Indeed, the traditional educational system forces parents and teachers to be satisfied with their children's success. They have no ability to broaden their thinking abilities. They do not able to associate themselves with the development of other countries' students'. They are satisfied with the little success of their children like teachers, engineers, doctors etc. Infact, parents play with the passions of the children. Except this professional achievement there are many things to be achieved like artist, singer, painter, photographer and so on. The present education system does not give proper cope to rejuvenate the latent talents of the learners. In the institution teachers emphasize only on curriculum based learning and creates such an atmosphere where students read only for getting high marks and degrees for getting a job.

This competitive race of high marks makes them uncreative learners. When they openly think about their achievements, they find a huge gap between their present profession and their actual passions. Behind their unsuccessful life ,the education system plays a important role. Even parents having been concerned about their children' actual desires they make them follow the strict rules of institution and lead them to be a doctor, teacher or an engineer. There are many stories that even after getting a successful job many persons leave their job and attach themselves to their inborn passions like singing or painting. Infact, the present rigid education system does not able to enter into a learner's emotional state ,what they actually like

or dislike. This is a huge mistake of the authority who frames education system. Although there are many positive recommendations on education like NCF-2005 which is framed for the overall development of the students, but it is just written, there are no actual output of this framework. To materialize the system we all should come together in one stage and should recreate the actual process of learning through reforming basic things of our education System.

In a survey, it is said that India produces engineers more than the total population of Switzerland, even after that Switzerland is the number one in research and innovation since independence, even in a report published by European Innovation Scoreboard in June 2021 the EC stated that Switzerland's strength's are in attractive research systems, human resources and intellectual assets. The USA achieved a hundred plus. On other hand, India has produced zero noble laureates in science. According to ASER(Annual status of Education Report) 83% of educated Indians is not employable. To find out the root cause behind this consequence we will have to go a little back, when British governments were ruling India, there are two major challenges for the East India Company, first the communication with Indian people and second, how to make Indian slaves through their administrative rules. They wanted Indians in their official works only for following their ideologies. They did not actually give importance to an Indian's high education. Britishers just wanted to use indians' intellectual abilities for the sake of their own benefit so that they could establish their western culture through promoting British institutions.

Thus, Britishers created education system which is basically formed on rigid rules and regulations. Even after independence Indians follow such education system where the democracy of the citizen has been degrading day by day. There is a competition of rote learning. A child after learning English for 12 years achieves nothing, even he can not speak English properly. On the other hand a child who can speak English fluently without books. Behind this discrimination of learning ,there is huge gap of providing education to different learners. we do not try to seek out psychological state of a child. We force them to learn what we teach. But we do not enquire the internal conditions of their minds. Every students has unique way of learning, we should find out their individual differences. John Locke said in his theory "Tabula Rasa" or "Blank Slate" that the children come in the world with the empty mind, and that knowledge and learning is received through experiences and converted to understanding through reasoning. Through their different stages of development we can find out their basic demands ,desires, wishes and so on. On fulfilling their individual demands we should teach them properly. But present education system does not create such atmosphere for actual development of the children. The teaching method for improving all round development of the learners, we should form a system where the children can focus on their original thoughts, passions, desires ,creativities .We always follow strict rules like $(a+b)^2=a^2+2ab+b^2$, rather than their divergent thinkings. Through adopting this process only 2% students can explore their creative ideas in India. This paper,thus presents the original conditions of the Indian learners and seeks for better approach for the upcoming learners of the Indian society.

If we compare our education system with other countries like Finland, South Korea, we would see a huge difference in every parts of education. We know Finland has the best education system of the world. Because there are no homework pressures on the students. They are provided various scopes to exhibit their latent talents. The education is completely free from rote learning. In the class, teachers give them freedom to perform their creative tasks. Extra-curricular based learning is one of the important methods of learning new things. Out side the text of the books, teacher gives student the proper stages to nurture their inborn passions. Bookish knowledge are completely unfollowed. The real work based teaching is the best method to understand the complex things easily. Our teaching should be based on everyday life's experience of the learners so that they easily comprehend the subject matter and thus they would utilize their practical knowledge in every matters. We should follow the education system of Finland so that major learners would be successful in reaching their actual goals. This is easy to say in writing format, but it is very difficult to materialize the reformation of education system in this country.

The socio- cultural and political system do not run smoothly. As a result no actual development occurs for the children. If the educationists emphasis on this vital issue ,it can be initiated .The process of teaching should be based on practical knowledge so that the learners can interlink their learning with their practical habits. For reaching to such goal we have to build strong infrastructure in the institutions. We should focus on child -centric education where the children can play their actual roles for self development Chetan Bhagat through his novel "Five Point someone" highlights the major problems of Indian education system and attempts to get aware about the prevailing education system to the common people. In this novel we find three important characters Hari, Ryan, Alok who were the mechanical students of IIT Bombay. Hari ,the narrator of the story, plays a vital role against the rigid education system. He did not like the traditional approach of learning where parents play passive roles for their children. Parents are always influenced by the traditional learning system. There are some specific wishes for parents positive attitude towards complex education process. Parents always want to see their children to be as a doctor, enginner, teacher etc. They think about a safe job for their children in future. But they do not want to give scopes their children to do other innovative tasks like dancing, singing, painting etc as there are no secure places for improving in the matter of earning money. This is happened because there are no proper infrastructures to make the parents believe that through creative abilities a child can develop his position widely. Thus, Chetan Bhagat wants to make aware the common people and the government and seeks a better method for all round development of the Indian children.

We know US has been top in education system. They have given huge opportunities to promote the children's skill and also have wide areas for higher education. A huge number of learners from the different countries want to go US for education. The United States of America (USA) hosts the most numbers of international students in the world. Unique curriculum, quality education,

multicultural environment and abundant opportunities are just the reasons why many students want to study in US. There are multi process of learning in US, as a result there are no problems to promote the innovative and creative thinking in the higher education. There are some important characteristic feature of US education system. Academic excellence is the major important factors in globalizing education process. In a survey ,2019 it is reported that out of 100 top universities, US has 33 universities. As a result there are lot of opportunities to admit such universities to improve the learners creative and critical thinking. The infrastructure of such universities are so unique for students to widen their innovative and extra- curriculum activities. Flexible education system is one of the most important features of US education system. American universities and colleges offer numerous opportunities to proceed their innovative thinking. There are many courses and programs to choose. You have the freedom to not only select the course content, but also the structure. At the undergraduate level you have the liberty to pursue different courses before they you declare your major at the end of the second year.

This helps to explore your subject interest and then decide without much hurry. Similarly, for your graduate studies you can choose your preference and when progress upon dissertation, you can focus on the ideas, you want to emphasize upon. American universities understand the struggle of international students, and they arrange regular programs, workshops and trainings to offer assistance. Cultural diversity is the most crucial factor to inter-nationalize the education system of United States of America. The US is a melting pot of different cultures, races and ethnicities. This diverse environment ensures to accept all communities to further progress their critical ideas over different areas. There is a no room for any sort of discrimination. You will get the students from different regions of the world while learning thereby making it rich and stimulating education experiences. Growing in the midst of diversity will provide you personality traits and skills that will be valuable in the international market. These days employers give importance to such people who learn from diversity culture. Lively and vibrant campus life also signify the good education system of US.It gives you wide areas to emphasize your new ideas. These greatest features leads US in the first place in developing all round development of the learners. On other hand India also have greatest policies to improve the education system like NCF-2005,NPE-2020,but there are no proper infrastructures to follow such policies easily.This paper thus wants to concern the Indian goverment to make the proper shape of education system so that our students should not go abroad for improving their creative and innovative power.

The novel of Chetan Bhagat,"Five Point Someone" bears the exact message what should be the proper education system for our country to make self- dependent.

Schools should play key role to nurture creativity and other skills of the learners. The recent international OECD-CCE- Singapore workshop gave 30 education decision makers from 12 countries the opportunity to share the lessons from Asian educational initiative aiming to foster pupils' creativity and critical

thinking. Singapore and Korea are two good examples of countries emphasizing creativity, critical thinking and character building in their curricula. Korea expects its schools to foster creativity as part of quality based learning- but also to devote almost 10% of overall school time to projects and other transversal activities that foster creativity. As for Singapore their “Desired Outcomes of Education” include critical and inventive thinking as well as social and emotional competences. At the end of secondary school, among other things students are expected to be “resilient in the face of adversity,” “innovative and enterprising” as well as “able to think critically and communicate persuasively.” In the schools of Singapore, creativity and innovation are at the heart of the project in elementary education. Teachers have developed common criteria to monitor their students’ progress in “critical thinking” and in “creative and inventive thinking.”

Students also assess themselves and their peers by answering questions such as I am able to brainstorm multiple ways to reach a solution (critical thinking) or “I am able to connect ideas I’m an interesting and creative manner to create a unique idea”(creative thinking).On other hand Indian students face difficulty in developing their creative and critical thinking. There are many reasons behind this problems. There are lack of resources by which pupils explore their innovative ideas. Lack of direction also affects the creative abilities. There are very short time to inter act on novel things between teachers and students. As a result students do not share new ideas to their teachers. Being afraid of failure is one of the most important factors not to forward their creative power. Students always have lack of confidence to nurture their innovative thinking as there is structure of getting more marks to be achieved high grade and thus promote to next class. In Indian education system we find an environment where students can not be autonomous character. They always depend on their teachers, the teachers always give them a specific instruction to follow. Thus the process of learning has been so rigid and difficult for the learners to focus on their individual uniqueness. In the novel “Five Point Someone” we find the character Professor Cherman is the antagonist. Though he is the head of the mechanical department and is fairly old, students are extremely scared of him. He plays a rigid role in school who does not give importance to students creative and innovative thinking. Infact, he was completely unconcerned about students’ critical thinking as he himself became a teacher through mugging up and memory test. Thus, the writer, through presenting this character symbolizes the actual condition of the Indian education system.

Five Point Someone is a novel by Chetan Bhagat that explains about the lives of three students at Indian Institute of Technology, one of the best universities in India. The story runs through three main characters, Hari, Ryan and Alok. The book takes us through the perspective Hari here, with shorts excerpts from his friends and girlfriend too. Hari is a middle class boy whose family details are not well described in the story. Alok, coming from a poor family faces a lot of difficulties before coming to IIT. And Ryan Oberoi, a rich class boy who thinks of a life as a piece of cake, caring to have all the fun he wants and avoiding his parents for not being with him.

The story takes us through the life in IIT and the difficulties students have to face. Ryan and Alok have very different perspectives and this always leads them to a fight. Ryan always tries to mug everything up, and Ryan, who thinks that someone should really know what they are doing are different here. The main highlight comes here when Cherian, the father of Hari's girlfriend, Neha who he meets early in the story, appears in his third year. Cherian happens to hate Hari and his friends for their low grades. The story really takes you through what students really face through. Categorised by their GPA's, there is distinct margin of care the teachers give for high scores and low scores. Hari, Ryan and Alok, all having a 5 point GPA are some low-scorers. Having to sit till morning for studies and notes, assignments, semesters etc to prepare for, their life is made a hell by the Institute. The rigid education system of IIT makes their live unbearable. They have no scopes to explore their innovative ideas and have no positive atmosphere to make them satisfied with their achievements. It has already been discussed that students of India face many problems to lead their lives through their favourite zones. They are pressurized by the whole process of education system and also by socio- cultural influence. Parents always play passive roles to nurture their kid's creative and innovative thinkings. Thus, Chetan Bhagat wrote this novel to make the common people do aware about the learners psychological state. This novel also talks about what the education system should be, that is based on concept understanding rather than rote learning. The writer paints a picture of various types of students here. There is a truly captivating plot in this novel. Chetan Bhagat doesn't let the readers attention diverge. The narration of the story is so interesting. The readers easily grasp its taste by thinking through the heart and easily realize the impact of the rigid process of Indian education.

This paper also discusses on the film was adopted from the novel, "Five Point Someone". The name of the film is "3 Idiots" directed by Rajkumar Hirani. The film "3 Idiots" plays similar features like the novel, but there are some controversies on this adoption. In this film, we find three main characters, Farhan, Raju, and Rancho. The story highlights the major problems of the Indian education system. It shows us how the pressure of parents turns a student into a unsuccessful character. The socio-cultural and political system negatively impacts on the development of the learners. Indian education system follows a rigid pattern to develop the intellectual power of the students, as a result, the students can not reach their goals. In the the story of the film, we find these three characters who share a room in a hostel at the Imperial College of Engineering, one of the best colleges in India. Farhan and Raju are average students of modest backgrounds, Rancho is from a rich family. Farhan wants to become wildlife photographer but has joined an Engineering college to fulfill his father's desires. Raju, on the other hand wants to uplift his family fortunes. Rancho is a wealthy genius who studies for the sheer joy of it. However Rancho's passion is for knowledge and taking apart and building machines rather than the conventional obsession of the other students with exam ranks. With his different approach, Rancho incures the wrath of dean of college.prof.Virus Sahastrabudhhe(Virus). Rancho irritates his lecture by giving creative and unorthodox answers, and confronts Virus

after fellow students Joy Lobo hangs himself in his dormitory room. This tragic incidents exposes the inhuman qualities of teachers and their professions. Rancho just picks out this tragic death and throws his straight views about education which can bring about destructive condition of the society. The role of Professor, Viru, Sahastrabudhhe(Virus) shows us the orthodox feature of education system, his conventionality creates a disorder condition for students' creative and innovative qualities. Through this inhuman pictures of teacher ,Chetan Bhagat wants the common people of this country to be concerned about the traditional approach of learning process and tries to give proper solutions by following alternative approach of learning new things by adopting the global education system which basically focuses on the students passions, desires, dream etc. Infact, this paper wants to give message that we should not emphasis on rote learning to fulfill parents' specific purpose, but we should seek out the students basic demands for learning, I.e. their creative abilities. We should give them freedom to find out their own interested areas in forwarding their learning process smoothly, then we must give them liberty to make set their careers. To materialize this process the whole educational process should be critically assessed and should make seminars to concern the parents by giving confidences that any kinds of creativities can make careers successfully. In this matter the authority of education system should lead a positive role to enhance this greatest approach. I say to mean that we should not write in black and white, we must go near to the unconscious people to give them practical knowledge and analyzes the whole process in simple language. If we follow this method ,then we can get the utmost result to reach our goals.

There are many eminent persons, poets, writers, scientists who give their valuable self assessments on the necessity of the creative education in India. The greatest Nobel laureates, Rabindranath says that the existing schools kills the natural desire of the child to be creative, it's sense of wonder. Tagore was of the view that creative learning could be encouraged only within a natural environment. He believes that education should not for mere "success" or "progress" but for "illumination of heart" and for inculcated of a spirit of sympathy, service and self sacrifice in the individual, so that the learners could rise above egocentric and ethnocentrism to a state of global consciousness. Tagore wants to give message that education can give us ideal environment to nurture our divine thoughts. We should not only focus on material achievements rather than individual enlightenment. According to Tagore, the aim of education is self realization. It means the realization of universal soul in one's self. it is a process which can not be realized without education. Tagore said that the medium of teaching instruction should be in mother tongue so that the children are able to express their emotions through learning new things. Moral and spiritual education is more important than bookish knowledge for an integral development of human personality. Indian famous scientist and educationist,A.P.J.Abdul Kalam Azad said that "creativity leads to thinking. Thinking provides knowledge. Knowledge makes you great".

He said that education is the most important element for growth and prosperity of a nation. He writes that we should mobilize resources for providing education to the underprivileged people. Dr. Kalam to be teacher right from the beginning Kalam gave message that the important aspect of creativity is “seeing the same thing as everybody else, but thinking of something different.” Kalam said this in his speech on “Innovation and Empowers Nation”. There are many greatest quotes of Kalam sir, just as he said “Don’t take rest after your first victory if you fail in second, more lips are waiting to say that your first victory was just a luck.” “Dream, dream, dream. Dreams transform into thoughts and thoughts result in action.” “To succeed in your mission, you must have single minded devotion to your goal” Kalam’s these famous quotes clearly hints that through individual experiences a learner can reach to his goal. Our famous independence leader and educationist Mahatma Gandhi brought an alternative approach of learning. He emphasized that handicrafts should be taught “not merely for production work but developing intellect of the pupils.” And this idea has been implemented in schools Socially Useful and Productive Work(SUPW) as per reports of landmark commissions and policy. According to Gandhiji “Craft art health and education should all the intregated into one scheme.”Nai Talim is a beautiful blend of all the four and covers the whole education of the individual from the time of conception to the moment of the death.....An education which does not teach us to discriminate between good and bad, to assimilate the one and eschew the other, is a misnomer. Education should be revolutionized as to answer the wants of the poorest villager, instead of answering those of an emperial exploiter. Eminent educationist of our country, Swami Vivekananda said that “Education is not the amount of information that we put into our brain and runs riot there, undigested all your life. We must have life building, man- making and character making assimilation of ideas. He said that “Education is the manifestation of perfection already in man.” men are born with the basic demands of learning, through teaching in perfect manner we can lead our lives with great illumination of thoughts. Through these above mentors’ views on education we can say that the way of teaching learning process should be dynamic and vivid in manner. Thus we can get a perfect environment where our ideas will be illuminated one day.

Indian education system should be assessed critically and should find out better approach for the new generation. There are critical problems to enhance the education process smoothly. Child labour is also major problem in Indian society. This socio- cultural conditions creates a long barrier to implement the whole education system. The child labour has not been stopped although there are strict laws on controlling this bad practice, but in reality ,there is a huge gap between the law and the implementation of the law. All things come under the political affairs, as a result no universal solution comes to stop this evil system of the society. In India there are many number of political parties which iinterfere to provide the basic rights of the common people but no one ends the problems by providing the requiring structure for best education. Poverty is the major problem in progressing the education system smoothly. The interference of different political parties plays

negative roles as they come with different rules and policy. At the end we see nothing changes after implementing different kinds of policies of different political parties. This paper wants to give message that until we would be together in developing the over all condition of the Indian society ,nothing would be achieved. And thus this major problem of education condition will not be removed. First we must remove the poverty from the society, then every steps for innovating the learning system will be reached to its zenith. Our education system is basically based on theortical approach rather than practical based. In a survey it is said almost 90% Indian learners learns through theortical base. To change this process we first should renovate the infrastructure of the Indian institutions. It will take long times, but we should start from now. One day obviously we would reach our dreams. This paper is not written only for reading carefully but also hints or suggests the education minister of India to play the active role for bringing universal achievement so that we can see our country after 20 years among the list of best 10 countries of the world in education system.

It is not denied that Indian educationists have not started their positives steps in improving the country from the rigid education system. Many educationists who have revolutionalized through starting innovative plans to enrich the curriculum system of Indian education. We have great thinkers like, Kiran Bir Shetty, who in the last 17 years has designed and executed a unique student centric curriculum. Her initiative like ‘Design for Change’ and FIDS (Feel, Imagine, Do & Share) have changed the mindset of the kids from ‘Can I’ to ‘I Can’. She has helped turn kids into real-life superheroes and innovate solutions for real life problems in their immediate environment and communities. DFC as a global movement, has touched 2.2 millions kids in 65 countries. She says “most often than not, in the misguided attempt to ‘teach’ our children, we forget that we need to ‘listen and learn’ from them. We are living curriculum, and our passions are ‘contagious’. So children’s live transform if teachers can remained their roles from ‘teaching’ to ‘reaching’ them – that is a great starting point.” Then we have another thinker, Omprakash Misra who first arrived at a government school in Odisha’s Koraput district to find out only two students. Gutted, buy not one to give up, he took care of everything, including their food, shelter and education. Moved by the sorry state of primary education where students from class 8 and 9 couldn’t add, substructure, multiply or divide, he co – authored Transit 1 for class 8 and Transit 2 for class 9, which helped students clear basic fundamental concept in 60 days. For tribal schools that lacked science labs and apparatus, he wrote ‘Experimento’ which helped teachers replicate science experiments in the syllabus with locally available and cheap. After this intervention kids scoring 90% in the district road from 3 to 32 in 2016.He gives messages to teachers by saying, “If you are true teacher, there are things you must keep in mind. Firstly, a good teacher is the one who reaches the level of the students to teach them, communicates easily and simplifies the most complex concepts. Second, learning is not a one way street. Be vibrant and connect your examples to real -life situations. Lastly, help them learn to live together. Values are important. Every students may or may not be doctor, enginner, teacher or one class officer.But they could become better individuals who

respect and live in harmony if shown how to.” Thus he contributes his role in reaching the expected goals of education. Next, we have thinker, Safeena Husain whose name is synonymous with successful education models in India, specially in rural areas, thanks to the spectacular work she has done through ‘Educate Girls’- founded in 2007. I feel one- size – fits all Will not work here. It is an iterative process. If you want to ensure quality education for all children on a larger scale, we must be ready individually institutionally, to focus solely on outcomes, identify the gaps, test and embrace new techniques/ approaches and keep improving on our successes. She says.

Enrolling children from difficult socio- economic backgrounds, using innovative models, improving learning outcomes and retaining them, Educate Girls’ latest venture, the Development Impact Bond has proven to be a real opportunity to transform the lives of the children. In this way Safeena Hussain plays her affirmative role in establishing real- life education . Next we find Beula Gabriel, who says “Teachers are game changers. They are the sculptors who mould the minds of students to greatness. They can be the North stars that guides generations to reach their goals. You are not preparing them for exams, you are preparing them for life. So arm them with those skills for life and build citizens with the highest moral values for the country.” Besides these great thinkers we know about Geeta Dharmaranjan, Rites Singh, Shaila Brijnath, Arghya Banerjee, Professor Sandip Desai who all give their valuable contributions in filling the gap of Indian education system.

If we attempt to investigate the history Indian educational system, we find many laws were implemented to reform the traditional education system of India. It was started from British rulers. The Indian Education Act 1835 was a legislative act of the council of India gave effect to a decision in 1835 by Lord William Bantick, then governor General of British East India Company to reallocate the funds. It was required by the British Parliament to spend on education and literature. There are many educational policies in India after independence. First we find Radha Krishnan Commission or Higher education commission(1948). This commission was established to investigate the Indian university education system and make recommendations for improvements. But there are some drawbacks in this commission. No clearcut suggestion was given for the medium of education. On the one hand, the commission accepted the medium of higher education in India should be through the regional languages and on the other hand it suggested the use of English till the regional languages develop to that extent. Then comes Mudaliar or Secondary Commission (1952).

This Commission also have many demerits. The suggestions are given in haste, so problems are still there. There are no statements regarding the improvement of social and economic conditions of the teachers. We do not find any suggestions to improve women education. There was still stress statements on English language. In the examination system we find many faults. Rigid time- table and unsuitable text books were given by the commission. There were no proper arrangements of co-curricular activities in the schools and no proper criteria for appointment of teachers.

Next we have Kothari Commission (1964-66) also known as National Education Commission of India. It was an ad hoc commission set up by the government of India to examine all aspects of the educational sector in India, to develop a general pattern of Education and to recommend guidelines and policies for the development of education in India. This commission recommended free and compulsory education for children aged 6 to 14 years, three language formula, encouragement of regional languages, distance education etc. But this commission also have problems to direct its objectives clearly. There are irrelevant lack of explanations. It suggested few solutions but doesn't give an explanation for their implementation or how to achieve it. The transformation of education system, as per Kothari Commission, requires a lot of financial investment. But there are no equilibrium condition to maintain economic investment in education. Whatever ,through this commission Indian education starts its innovative approach for developing the nation. After that we find NPE in 1968, which is the extended form of Kothari Commission. It creates policy for fulfilling compulsory education for all children upto the age of 14. It aims to spend 6% of the national income to education. This commission was introduced by the PM Rajib Gandhi which brings policy to emphasis on the removal of disparity and to equalize educational opportunity, specially for Indian women scheduled tribes and scheduled castes communities. In 1986 ,an another National Education Policy has been implemented which plays positive role in empowering women education. It also emphasizes on improving technical education. It fosters the development of new values through redesigned curricula, text books, the trainings and the orientation teachers, decision makers and administrators and the active involvement of educational institutes. This policy was reformed in 1992. It basically focuses on modernization and role of IT in education. This policy having good features also bears negative impact in maintaining the standard norms to reach over all development. This policy has recommended the institution of capitation fees for admitting students in technical institutions. Thus, this policy can not be accepted as a healthy policy, as this is likely to deprive many deserving students of obtaining technical education, if they can not pay such a fee. And finally we get new National Education Policy in 2020 which will be discussing in the next paragraph.

A new National Education Policy has been recently formed by Indian Union Cabinet Minister Dr.Kastariranjana, July 29 ,2019. NEP -2020 has been brought to improve India's Education system, ranging from elementary school to college. Many People applaud this recently because it speaks of big transformational changes in the Indian educational sector. Along with this praise, there is critique, which reflects on the flaws of this current educational policy. Through this policy, the government hopes to make Education accessible to everyone. This policy aims to take back approximately 2 crores student in the educational institutions. This policy will replace the previous structure 10+2 and bring 5+3+3+4 structure. NCERT will plan and create a national curricular and pedagogical framework for Early Childhood Care and Education for children under the age of 8. The Education Ministry will create a national mission on foundational literacy and numeracy. The States of India are

responsible for successfully implementing the base numeracy and literacy for all children before they reach class 3. NCERT, SCERT, s and the national council for teacher education will establish a shared national professional standards for teachers by 2022, in collaboration with teachers and specialist organizations (NPST). Thus this policy brings so many innovative ideas to change the whole education system of India. But there is a big question whether this policy would be possible to implement. Because there are lack of institutional infrastructures. This NEP undoubtedly plans to transform Indian educational system through reforming the rigid systems, but in practically whether we can reach our goals or not, that is the question. There are socio-economic barriers to implement this policy as we know India is a country of many languages and has lack of infrastructures. In this multilingual country how a teacher can teach through mother tongue languages.

Thus, Language is a negative consideration because India has a troublesome teacher – students ratio, making it difficult to introduce mother tongues for each subjects in academic institutes. Finding a qualified instructor can be difficult at times, and the launch of NEP 2020, which includes taking research materials in mother tongue has added difficulty. According new NPE – 2020, students who wish to complete their education must prepare for four years, while a diploma degree can be completed in as little as two years .This will allow the students to drop out of the course in the middle. Students in private schools will be exposed to English at a far young age than students in government schools, according to the national education strategy,2020. The academic curriculum will be taught to government school’s students’ in their respective ethnic languages. This is one of the big recent school reform flaws that it would raise the percentages of students who are awakened talking In English, deepening the social divide. These all are vital problems to implement the new educational policy. The proposed reform by NEP- can be implemented by a partnership between federal and state governments. But we know how the relation between state and Central governments are. They are looking as their enemies at each and every steps. This paper aims to achieve a system where no political parties would interfere to change the system as there are lacks of union in thought and works. We should look for a neutral association in the country so that there would be no discrepancy in implementing the educational reform. For doing this thing an autonomous body should play positive role where no political face would give their opinions. We should assess the global education system which has already been discussed in this paper. How other countries, like Finland, USA, Sweden have created a greatest atmosphere of creative and critical education. The writer, Chetan Bhagat, thus, attempts to enlighten our thought process through narrating sensible story in the novel “Five Point Someone.”

This paper aims to widen the educational system of India by giving some points which should be followed step by step. The following points will be discussed step by step.

Ways to Nurture Creativity: Creativity is not an injection which you can give to someone. For creativity you need to create an environment for curiosity as a way to encourage students and gets best of them. Teacher can play the most important play in nurturing creativity among students. How as the teachers must be trained massively in various ways to nurture creativity thinking in the students.

Experimental Learning and Exploration: There is an urgent to shift focus from passive learning to experimental learning I.e. learning by doing. By engaging students to hands up practical experiments and reflections they are better able to connect theories and knowledge learned in the classroom to real world situations.

New Teaching Learning Methods: Students need to be encouraged to ask innumerable ways why's and why not's. Curiosity is the seed of creativity. By encouraging curiosity, we can train our's students to become independent thinking individuals who discover and solve problems own their own and thus nurturing their confidence and self belief.

Avoid Excessive Use of Internet: One of the main reasons behind the lack of creativity in our students is the excessive usage of internet. This has impacted adversely the generation of original ideas and plans. Students do not bother to use their imagination while preparing a project or report and dissertation and what is worse is that the institutions do not object.

ICT Empowered Pedagogies: In this information age, teachers need to be empowered with the new ICT Empowered pedagogies such as blended learning and flipped classroom which can help to reach the targeting goals in 21st century. The main goal of the flipped classroom is to enhance student learning and achievement by reversing the traditional method of teaching.

Focus on Keen Observation: Keen observation of the world around has caused many important break through in science and medicine and in social and business world. Observation skills are found to be greatly linked to greater creativity, originality and flexible thinking.

Reforms in Assessment Pattern: Assessment drives learning. Special training needs to be given to the teachers through workshops in setting examinations' questions which test out the creative thinking of the learners. Assessment process needs to be made more scientific to encourage multiple skills of the students. The way we asses our students, the students will in that way.

Lighter Syllabi: There is a need to have lighter syllabi in each discipline consisting of only core essentials and the focus of teaching should be on conceptual clarity. All of this will give the students ample time to be the creative thinkers.

Teaching Beyond Curriculum: At least one lecture per week should be developed to 'teaching Beyond curriculum'. In this lecture students may be asked to decide what they will like to do in one year or in one semester. This project may

involve anything like writing poetry, news report, general articles and scientific fantasies.

Through following such methods we can reach our actual goal to make the country self depended and self resourceful. There are many criticisms on Chetan Bhagat's writing styles. Bhagat was a student of Army Public School. From childhood he was experimenting the traditional approaches of the society. The socio-cultural conditions make him conscious for writing works on new subjects which seeks a novel path to reform the various problems of the contemporary society. Slandering Chetan Bhagat is one thing loves to do. Criticizing someone on facts is an ideal thing to do it and many do it so. However, slandering someone without knowing the works of a writer shows the critiques' imprudence attitude. Many readers and book reviewers of India have criticized Chetan Bhagat's books by judging from one angle. They claimed that his writings style is sombre and singular. His novels are shallow and without literary richness and one timed read. I think the critiques overlapped to judge his motto of writings. If we go into the depths of his writings, it will be surprising discovery. The author has tried to portray the issues that the populations of the time faces day in and day out. Relationship, Love, Friendship, Job, Frustration, Dreams, Heartbreak, Break-up and Hook up, One Night Stand, Sex, Movies, Politics and Governments' – things that synchronize with the thoughts of today's generation feature in works of Chetan Bhagat. Thus, this paper defends the charges against Bhagat's writings style. The conventional reviewers views on Chetan Bhagat's writings have become worthless when we read the novel "Five Point Someone" and it's adopted film "3 Idiots". This work of Bhagat enlightens the people of traditional society. The common people are able to realize the boring education system and seeks an alternative method for learning education so that the creative and critical thinking of the children would be precisely evaluated. Through this way, we can say that Chetan Bhagat is undoubtedly a greatest writer of this age. His works shows us right path to improve our overall condition. His novel ideas enlighten our thought process and enrich the overall condition of the people of Indian society.

Conclusion:

In conclusion we can say that Chetan Bhagat is a versatile figure who works as a novelist, scriptwriter, journalist and public intellectual. If you haven't ever read a single book and you do not know where to start then Chetan Bhagat is a very good starting point. In fact, a person can immediately connect with the characters in his books. Chetan Bhagat, an embodiment of phenomenal success in writing world, who defined the publication industry in a country not known for its readers. Probably the only author from the country who boasts of a celebrity status. He is the biggest English selling novelist in Indian history as per New York Times. Chetan Bhagat has a vivid style of writings with all his novels in third person. Once When asked about the numbers as his novel titles, he humorously replied to reporters that he is a banker, he can't get numbers out of his head. There is a significance of the name 'Chetan' which means "Spirit Full" or "full of Consciousness" derived from Sanskrit word, 'Chaitanya'. Bhagat is famous for his creative and innovate writings which brings

about the changes of the contemporary society. “Five Point Someone” is probably a nice book according to me. It is worth reading book which exposes the traditional rigid education system of India. The term “Five Point Someone” refers to a person who ranked at the bottom of their class according to their GPA. It is commentary and social critique of the education system. In this novel Chetan Bhagat gives clear vision about Indian education system which has been blindly following by the Indian people without knowing the fact. Through this book ,the writer challenges to such traditional passive features of education system and tries to give ideas of best method to teach the learners through inventing the creative power in different areas. The adopted film, “3 Idiots” also have the same purpose to generate the ideas of individual character. In this way we can quote famous speech of Chetan Bhagat

“Privileged classes and the new aspirational need to learn to co- exist with each other. The old elite need to understand the new reality where privilege no longer gives you instant entitlement or monopoly over public opinion. Aspirational has to learn to articulate and conduct itself well and remain open minded to others. In the Great Indian Opinion Wars, may the best opinion for India win, whichever side it comes from.”

--Chetan Bhagat, India Positive:

New Essays and Selected Columns

Through researching the innovative features of Chetan Bhagat's writings, we can say that the great writer, Chetan Bhagat has become a unique figure in changing the outdated method of Indian education and his views on the whole condition of Indian education system has been considered a valuable resource for up coming society. After the above critical study, I can say that the core purpose for writing this research article has been reached to its zenith in its destination and this paper also have a strong suggestion to have a farther research on this unique topic.

References :

- Bhagat, Chetan. Five Point Someone, New Delhi: Rupa & Co. ,2004. Print.
- Varma, Pavan K. The Great Indian Middle Class, New Delhi: Penguin Books, 2007.
- ASER, Annual Status of Education Report, 2014, Available at: <http://img.asercentre.org/docs/Publications/ASER2014/NationalPPTs/aser2014indiaenglish.pdf> [Accessed May 16, 2015].
- Chudgor,A.,Educationforcreativity.LiveMint.Availableat:
<http://www.livemint.com/Opinion/5pNP5TgamzR9roigcRMu71/Education-for-creativity.html> [Accessed May 16, 2015]
- Guimbal, A., How to create a better school system. The Indian Express, p. 15. 2015. Available at: <http://indianexpress.com/article/opinion/columns/how-to-create-a-better-school-system/> [Accessed May 16, 2015].

Kanaiyalal Patel, Sneha. “Contemporary Indian English Campus novels : A Study of its Significant Aspects” IJELLH, Vol. 6 no.9, 2016, pp. 404-416.
www.ijellh.com.

Mukherjee, R., Indian Education System: what needs to change? Unlawyered, NationalUniversityofJuridicalSciences.2013.Availableat:<http://startup.nujs.edu/blog/Indian-education-system-what-needs-to-change/> [Accessed May 16, 2015].

John, Prashant. Second Degree. Eklavaya Education Foundation, 2009.

Interview. Listen to your Heart: Bhagat, Times of India 22 Nov. 2009. Web.

Peat, F.D., Creativity and Education. Bibliography Essays. Available at:
<http://www.f davidpeat.com/bibliography/essays/dempsey.htm> [Accessed May 16 2015].